

CHILDREN'S IMMUNITY AND CAUSES OF INDEPENDENCE

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According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 82% of children suffer from various levels of anemia. Low levels of hemoglobin and iron deficiency cases of various etiologies lead to mental and physical disabilities in the child. The main causes of anemia in children are:

- Lack of a complete, balanced diet;
- Impaired absorption of iron in the gastrointestinal tract;
- Disorders of vitamin metabolism;
- Parasitic diseases;
- Dysbacteriosis, gastritis, gastroduodenitis and other gastrointestinal diseases;
- Hormonal imbalances;
- Environmental factors: heavy metal poisoning, air, water and food pollution, etc.

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ABSTRACT

The need for iron in children varies with age and depends on sexual factors as they reach puberty. Treatment of deficient anemias in children with a balanced diet is not always effective, so experts prefer to use additional drugs to normalize the micronutrients and vitamins in the child's body.

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Iron deficiency anemia in children can lead to other diseases. This is because patients with anemia are more likely to develop other infectious diseases. Anemia in children is treated by a pediatrician, and in severe cases by a hematologist. Pediatric anemia is a problem for pediatricians around the world. Decreased hemoglobin in the blood can lead to anemia. The delivery of oxygen to the brain is the main function of hemoglobin in the blood. Patients with this disease and low immunity are at higher risk of developing various infectious diseases. Blood contains nutrients that are essential for the body's growth and development.

The main function of erythrocytes is to transport oxygen molecules. Oxygen is delivered to organs and tissues through a special protein called hemoglobin. You can see the average hemoglobin level in the following numbers:

Normal hemoglobin level in G / L (grams per liter) depends on age:

- in newborns - from 180 to 240;
- 1 month to 5 years - from 110 to 115;
- 5 to 12 years - from 110 to 120;
- 12 to 15 years old - 120 to 140 years old.

The main causes of anemia. Anemia in children develops for a variety of reasons. Parents should carefully determine the cause of the disease. Anemia is caused by external and internal, hereditary and acquired, pregnancy and postpartum, pathological and underlying factors. A woman's anemia during pregnancy can affect a baby. Unfortunately, the number of anemias caused by a doubling of iron requirements in pregnant women is high. Anemia is a dangerous disease for children. This is because the child grows day by day, and it is known that if he does not have enough "reserves", he may lag behind in development. Malnutrition and lack of vitamin-rich foods can also cause anemia. Prolonged low levels of hemoglobin in the body can lead to hypoxia, or lack of oxygen in the child. As a result, organs and tissues are damaged. Because of anemia, children may lag behind in physical and intellectual development. They are also prone to chronic and infectious diseases.

Symptoms of the disease. Anemia affects many organs and systems. The first signs appear on the skin and become pale and soft. Nails and hair become brittle and

lose their shine. Frequent inflammation of the tongue and superficial wounds may occur. Anemia also affects the nervous system. Anemia can cause tinnitus and dizziness. The most striking symptom of anemia is constant fatigue and malaise. Worst of all, children under the age of 1 are lagging far behind their peers. In severe cases, it can even cause fainting and heart palpitations. Anemia can also cause low blood pressure.

Classification of anemia. Anemia is classified based on its etiology, disease progression, stage of anemia, and diagnostic criteria.

Anemia in infants. A newborn baby is supplied with iron from the mother's body during development in the womb. Physiological decrease in hemoglobin in the blood is observed in infants born at 4-5 months of age, and in premature infants at 3 months of age, when the system of self-formation of blood is defective and rapid physical growth.

Artificial and mixed nutrition is one of the risk factors that increases the likelihood of anemia. In particular, hemoglobin deficiency develops as a result of the replacement of breast milk and / or artificial supplements with cow's, goat's milk, porridge by 9-12 months. Symptoms of anemia in children under one year of age include: skin discoloration, "transparency", "blueness" of the skin because the skin layers are still very thin;

- Anxiety, crying for no reason;
- Sleep disorders;
- Low appetite;
- Excessive physiological and normal hair loss;
- Frequent recurrence;
- Slow weight gain;

- Lack of physical and then psychological development, lack of interest, lack of expression of the recovery complex, etc.

A distinctive feature of children of this age is the ability to absorb iron very well (up to 70%), so many pediatricians do not prescribe drugs for anemia in infants, but simply adjust the child's diet, to determine the transfer to breast milk. If the condition is severe, iron supplements may be prescribed according to age.

When severe anemia is diagnosed, it may be due to disease, pathology, or dysfunction of the child's body, rather than diet. Anemia can also be caused by inherited diseases. If hemoglobin levels in children are consistently low, the underlying cause should be identified and treated.

Anemia in preschool children. A large-scale study in 2010 found that iron deficiency anemia in preschool children is common and widespread: one in two children suffers from hemoglobin deficiency due to low iron levels. The etiology of this condition can vary - but most often it is caused by persistent anemia in the early stages of life.

The second factor that contributes to anemia in preschool children is often similar to the first factor. Malnutrition, lack of protein (meat products) and vitamins (vegetables), as a result of frequent consumption of semi-finished products and sweets, the child does not want to eat meat and vegetables. It depends only on the upbringing of the parents.

If the child's diet is normal and he still shows signs of anemia (white skin, rapid fatigue, dry skin, brittle nails), it is recommended to see a specialist. Although

9 out of 10 anemic children develop anemia due to iron deficiency, in 10% of cases it develops due to various diseases and pathologies (celiac disease, leukemia).

Anemia in primary school children. The hemoglobin level in children aged 7-11 years is 130 g / l. During this period, the symptoms of anemia gradually increase. Emerging anemia often results in acute respiratory viral and bacterial infections, fatigue, and inattention that can affect school students' learning outcomes.

Another important factor in the development of anemia in children attending educational institutions is the inability to control their diet. Children of this age still have a high ability to absorb iron (10%, and in adults this figure is 3%), so the diet for the treatment of iron deficiency anemia in children of this age should be rich in vitamins and minerals. Filling with is important.

Inactivity, lack of fresh air, and sitting alone at home, especially playing tablets, smartphones, and computers, can lead to staying in one position for long periods of time, which in turn can lead to anemia.

Adolescent anemia. During adolescence, the risk of anemia increases, especially in girls, with the onset of the menstrual cycle, and regular blood loss does not go unnoticed. The second factor that contributes to the development of anemia in adolescent girls is their concern for their appearance and the introduction of different diets and dietary restrictions to correct their figure.

During this period, rapid growth, active sports, and malnutrition affect adolescents of both sexes. Symptoms of anemia in adolescence include bruising of the sclera of the eye, changes in the shape

of the nails, disorders of the digestive system, changes in taste and smell.

Certain forms of the disease during adolescence require medical treatment. When following the instructions of a specialist during treatment, changes in the blood occur after 10-12 days, and after 6-8 weeks there is an improvement in the general condition.

Thus, the importance of prevention and treatment of anemia is enormous. Anemia in children should not be ignored. This pathology is more serious than any other disease and as a result, the child's life may change dramatically. Therefore, it is important to prevent anemia in time, because it is better and easier to prevent than to treat.

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